

An Efficient Low-order Integral Transport Matrix Method for Optically Thick Problems Implemented in Griffin

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a new low-order integral transport matrix method (LITMM) based on the truncation of small-magnitude entries in the integral transport matrix (ITM) for DFEM-SN discretizations of the neutron transport equation has been developed. The integral transport matrix method (ITMM) enables solving fixed source problems by constructing and solving a global linear system without requiring source iterations. However, the direct solution of the linear system is expensive since it involves a dense matrix, and the cost of constructing the ITM is immense. In the current work, we developed a dynamic truncation scheme that truncates ITM entries smaller than a user-specified threshold on the fly, thus reducing the construction cost of the full ITM, and leading to a sparse low-order operator. The sparse structure of the new matrix allows for the use of Krylov subspace solvers, thereby reducing the expense of solving the global linear system. We implemented the LITMM in the particle transport code Griffin to solve one-speed, fixed-source problems as both a solver and a preconditioner for Richardson iterations with isotropic scattering. We utilized a three-dimensional cubic geometry problem comprised of two regions for testing the method by altering the optical thickness and truncation threshold for constructing the LITM. We compared the LITMM-based results with Griffin's DFEM-SN solutions on the same mesh. The results showed that the LITMM is an accurate low-order method that generates high-order equivalent solutions, and it is a computationally efficient preconditioner for Richardson iterations for optically thick problems.

Keywords: Low-order Transport Method, Optically Thick Problems, Integral Transport Matrix, Dynamic Truncation

1. INTRODUCTION

Solving the neutron transport equation (NTE) with source iterations is costly for configurations with low neutron dissipation, such as scattering-dominated and optically thick media. Therefore, low-order neutron transport models, such as the diffusion approximation and the simplified spherical harmonics (SPN) method, have been developed [1] at a lower cost by integrating out angular dependence. However, these low-order methods have limited accuracy when there are strong material discontinuities and strongly anisotropic scattering [2]. Therefore, developing low-order operators while maintaining solution accuracy is a hot topic in the neutron transport community. High-order neutron transport solution algorithms rely in some way on memory-efficient mesh sweeps. During the mesh sweeps, local linear systems are solved per mesh element per direction when the discontinuous finite element method (DFEM) and discrete ordinates (S_N) discretizations are employed, rather than constructing a global linear system. It is possible to build a global linear system in the scalar flux for the discretized NTE through the Integral Transport Matrix Method (ITMM). However, mesh sweeps are preferred because constructing and solving a global linear system is very expensive due to its dense structure.

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ITMM was first studied in [3]. Then Rosa *et al.* [4] showed that the magnitude of an entry in the Integral Transport Matrix (ITM) diminishes asymptotically with increasing optical distance between the two cells corresponding to the entry's row and column since the entry represents the coupling strength between these two cells. Furthermore, ITM has been developed mainly for zeroth-order local-expansion methods. The higher accuracy of first-order local-expansion methods motivates us to develop a new low-order DFEM-SN operator that is computationally efficient for optically thick problems.

We developed a low-order integral transport matrix method (LITMM), and implemented it in the Griffin code [5] both as a solver and as a preconditioner. The current implementation will be merged into the main GitHub branch upon completion of the research. The LITMM is obtained by truncating ITM entries with magnitude smaller than a specified threshold, yielding a low-order integral transport matrix (LITM). Additionally, we developed a dynamic scheme to truncate LITM entries during the construction stage, thereby eliminating the cost of constructing the full ITM. The LITM is sparse for optically thick problems, and this enables the use of Krylov subspace methods to solve the linear system efficiently, addressing another drawback of the ITMM.

In this paper, we first define ITM for DFEM-SN discretizations, then we develop the dynamic truncation algorithm and define the LITMM. Next, we describe the implementation of the LITMM in Griffin as a solver and as a preconditioner. We establish the accuracy of the LITMM as a solver by comparing its solution to the high-order DFEM-SN solution for a two-region cubic geometry problem with tetrahedral meshes. Finally, we test LITMM's performance as a preconditioner by comparing the computing time with Griffin's built-in Generalized Minimal Residual Method (GMRES) preconditioner with nonlinear diffusion accelerations (NDA). The results show that LITM is an accurate low-order operator when the truncation threshold is chosen judiciously, and the LITMM is more computationally efficient as a preconditioner than Griffin's built-in GMRES preconditioner for optically thick problems.

2. THEORY & METHOD

2.1. ITM for DFEM-SN Discretization

The neutron transport equation assuming isotropic scattering and fixed source for the m^{th} direction is

$$\vec{\Omega}_m \cdot \vec{\nabla} \psi_m(\vec{r}) + \Sigma_t \psi_m(\vec{r}) = \Sigma_s \phi(\vec{r}) + q(\vec{r}), \quad m = 1, \dots, M, \quad (1)$$

where Σ_t and Σ_s are the total and scattering macroscopic cross sections, respectively, $\phi(\vec{r})$ is the scalar flux, $q(\vec{r})$ is the fixed source, $\psi_m(\vec{r})$ is the angular flux, and $\vec{\Omega}_m$ is the m^{th} of total M discrete ordinates.

Griffin employs a linear DFEM for the spatial discretization [6] of the S_N equations yielding a discretized NTE in the form of a global linear system when vacuum boundary conditions are applied:

$$M_A \vec{\Psi}_m = M_B \Sigma_s \vec{\Phi} + M_B \vec{Q}, \quad m = 1, \dots, M, \quad (2)$$

where M_A and M_B are global finite element matrices, $\vec{\Psi}_m$ and $\vec{\Phi}$ represent the global angular and scalar flux expansion coefficient vectors, respectively. \vec{Q} holds the fixed source expansion coefficients, and Σ_s is a diagonal matrix with scattering cross sections. The size of the linear system is the total number of expansion coefficients in the discretized problem (N_e). Traditionally, the global DFEM matrices are not constructed; instead, spatial mesh element-based local linear systems (weighted balance equations) are solved via sweeps with source iterations. Inverting M_A on the LHS of Equation (2) yields,

$$\vec{\Psi}_m = L_m^{-1} \Sigma_s \vec{\Phi} + L_m^{-1} \vec{Q}, \quad m = 1, \dots, M, \quad (3)$$

where $L_m^{-1} = M_A^{-1} M_B$, represents the sweep operator for DFEM-SN discretizations for the m^{th} direction.

The scalar flux in the S_N method is obtained using Gauss quadrature integration, $\vec{\Phi} = \sum_{m=1}^M \omega_m \vec{\Psi}_m$, where ω_m is the m^{th} direction quadrature weight. The quadrature integrated scalar flux is,

$$\vec{\Phi} = \sum_{m=1}^M \omega_m \vec{\Psi}_m = \mathbf{W}\vec{\Psi}, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{W} is a rectangular $N_e \times MN_e$ matrix holding the quadrature weights and $\vec{\Psi}$ is the vector of all the angular flux expansion coefficients for all directions, i.e. $\vec{\Psi} = [\vec{\Psi}_1^T, \dots, \vec{\Psi}_M^T]^T$. Integrating Equation (3) over angle using Equation (4) results in the ITM form of the DFEM-SN discretized NTE:

$$\vec{\Phi} = \mathbf{A}(\Sigma_s \vec{\Phi} + \vec{Q}) \rightarrow \mathbf{B}\vec{\Phi} = \mathbf{A}\vec{Q}, \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{A} \equiv \sum_{m=1}^M \omega_m \mathbf{L}_m^{-1}$, $\mathbf{B} \equiv \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}\Sigma_s$ is called the ITM, and \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix. When this linear system is solved by inverting the ITM on the right hand side, the scalar flux distribution is immediately obtained. However, ITM is a dense matrix and this operation would be very expensive to solve directly.

2.2. Generation of ITM entries

To generate the ITM entries we use the fact that multiplying a standard basis unit vector \vec{e}_k whose k^{th} entry is 1, all other entries are zero, by a matrix yields the entries in the k^{th} column of the matrix. Recognizing \mathbf{A} as the mesh sweep **linear** operator, we perform a mesh sweep on the source vector \vec{e}_k to obtain the vector $\vec{\Phi}_k$ that is the k^{th} column vector of \mathbf{A} . In other words, ITM is comprised of the spatial distribution of the response to each unit scalar flux expansion coefficient in the discretized problem. First, mesh sweeps are performed on each source $\Sigma_s \vec{e}_k$, $k = 1, \dots, N_e$, to obtain $\vec{\Phi}_k = \mathbf{A}\Sigma_s \vec{e}_k$, $k = 1, \dots, N_e$. Then the ITM is assembled from all obtained column vectors, i.e. $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{I} - [\vec{\Phi}_1, \vec{\Phi}_2, \dots, \vec{\Phi}_{N_e}]$. However, construction of the full ITM is extremely costly, as it requires N_e mesh sweeps.

2.3. Low Order ITM and the Dynamic Truncation Scheme

The ITM entries represent the coupling between the scalar flux expansion coefficients. In the case of DFEM with Lagrange basis functions, the scalar flux expansion coefficients are nodal discontinuous scalar fluxes. The magnitude of the off-diagonal entries in ITM decreases with increasing optical distance between the coupled cells [4]. Accordingly, small entries in ITM can be truncated, resulting in a sparse matrix. We developed a dynamic scheme to truncate the negligible ITM entries during the construction phase, i.e. the mesh sweeps on \vec{e}_k source vectors. The truncation algorithm sets to zero the negligible angular flux responses during the mesh sweeps as follows. First, we define a sweep mask list (SML) that stores a flag whether an element in the spatial mesh is active for sweeping in a specific direction. The sweeps are performed only on mesh elements activated in the SML. Our algorithm starts the mesh sweeps by activating the mesh element containing the source in the SML. The order of the mesh elements in the SML is determined by a sweep path for each discrete ordinate that is adapted from the original sweep path to process the affected element first, followed by its downstream neighbors, since each e_k may occur at a different spatial location. Our algorithm identifies the first active mesh element in the SML and sweeps it. During the sweeps, the algorithm compares the computed nodal angular fluxes to a user-defined truncation threshold for the swept element:

- If the magnitude of at least one of the nodal angular fluxes is greater than the threshold, the spatial mesh element's coupling with the source-node is defined, and the algorithm activates downstream elements in the SML that share the current element's outgoing faces.
- If all nodal angular fluxes are smaller than the threshold, i.e. mesh element is weakly coupled, all nodal angular fluxes of the element are set to zero, and no adjacent elements are activated in SML.

As a result, sweeps are performed only for potentially coupled mesh elements, thus avoiding unnecessary sweeps for weakly coupled cells. First, all the angular flux responses are obtained for the k^{th} source vector \vec{e}_k for all discrete ordinates,

$$\vec{\Psi}_{k,m} = \tilde{L}_m^{-1} \Sigma_s \vec{e}_k, \quad (6)$$

where \tilde{L}_m^{-1} represents the truncated single direction sweep operator for the m^{th} discrete ordinate. Then the nodal scalar flux response is calculated by Gauss quadrature integration,

$$\vec{\Phi}_k = \sum_{m=1}^M \omega_m \vec{\Psi}_{k,m}. \quad (7)$$

Lastly, the magnitude of the scalar flux response is controlled: If the magnitude of at least one nodal scalar flux is greater than the threshold, the mesh element scalar fluxes are saved into the scalar flux response vector $\vec{\Phi}_k$. Finally, assembling the truncated $\tilde{A}\Sigma_s \leftarrow [\vec{\Phi}_1, \vec{\Phi}_2, \dots, \vec{\Phi}_{N_e}]$ matrix and subtracting it from the identity matrix yields the LITM, denoted \tilde{B} :

$$\tilde{B} = I - \tilde{A}\Sigma_s. \quad (8)$$

The LITM linear system is written as,

$$\tilde{B}\vec{\Phi} = A\vec{Q}, \quad (9)$$

where $\vec{\Phi}$ is the vector of low-order scalar flux DFEM expansion coefficients. The right hand side of the LITM linear system is obtained by performing single mesh sweep on the source vector. The LITM is sparse for optically thick configurations, consequently, we employ GMRES to solve the linear system Equation (9). The LITMM addresses the drawbacks of the ITMM by avoiding the construction and solution costs of a dense matrix equation. The scaling of the full ITM construction cost with respect to N_e is quadratic, making the method ineffective for large problems. In contrast, our numerical experiments on homogeneous problems with fixed optical thickness (not shown due to page limit) indicate that the LITM construction time and its memory consumption scale with orders ~ 1.06 and ~ 1.02 with N_e , respectively. These scalings are nearly linear, making LITMM better suited to large problems.

2.4. Implementation in Griffin

Griffin is a deterministic MOOSE-based particle transport code mainly developed for advanced reactor designs [5]. It uses DFEM for spatial discretization and S_N for angular discretization, and employs Richardson iterations that utilize the angular flux to converge the residual of the balance equation by using a proper preconditioner [7]. In contrast, LITMM operates on the scalar flux, hence, we modified our low-order operator to produce low-order angular fluxes. We investigated using LITMM as a preconditioner for Richardson iterations, as well as a solver. The discretized form of the NTE as a global linear system can be written in the following form:

$$(L - S)\vec{\Psi} = \vec{Q}, \quad (10)$$

where the variables have the same meaning as before, except here they are comprehensive vectors of size MN_e . Preconditioning this linear system requires an approximation of $(L - S)^{-1}$ that can be provided by LITM. The discretized transport equation can also be written in the form:

$$\vec{\Psi} = L^{-1}P\Sigma_s\vec{\Phi} + L^{-1}\vec{Q}, \quad (11)$$

where P is an operator that repeats the vector $\Sigma_s\vec{\Phi}$ M times to create a MN_e size vector. LITMM offers an approximate $\vec{\Phi}$, i.e. $\vec{\Phi} = \tilde{B}^{-1}WL^{-1}\vec{Q}$. Inserting this expression in Equation (11) and rearranging yields an approximate angular flux solution,

$$\vec{\Psi} = (L^{-1}P\Sigma_s\tilde{B}^{-1}W + I)L^{-1}\vec{Q}. \quad (12)$$

The angular flux distribution obtained with Equation (12) amounts to the implementation of LITMM as a low-order solver in Griffin. Equation (12) implies that $(L^{-1}P\Sigma_s\tilde{B}^{-1}W + I)L^{-1}$ is an approximation of $(L - S)^{-1}$ per Equation (10). We define the operator $(L^{-1}P\Sigma_s\tilde{B}^{-1}W + I)L^{-1}$ to be a modified LITM operator that generates angular fluxes. Applying it as a preconditioner to Equation (10) produces:

$$(L^{-1}P\Sigma_s\tilde{B}^{-1}W + I)L^{-1}(L - S)\vec{\Psi} = (L^{-1}P\Sigma_s\tilde{B}^{-1}W + I)L^{-1}\vec{Q}. \quad (13)$$

Adding $\vec{\Psi}$ to both sides of Equation (13), inserting iterative indices and lagging the variables on the right hand side by one iteration yields the LITM preconditioned Richardson iterations:

$$\vec{\Psi}^{l+1} = \vec{\Psi}^l + (L^{-1}\Sigma_s\tilde{B}^{-1}W + I)L^{-1}\vec{R}^l, \quad (14)$$

where $\vec{R}^l = \vec{Q} - (L - S)\vec{\Psi}^l$ is the residual in the l^{th} preconditioned Richardson iteration. To apply the operator $(L^{-1}\Sigma_s\tilde{B}^{-1}W + I)L^{-1}$ in Griffin we use mesh sweeps and the GMRES solver. First, our algorithm constructs the LITM using Griffin's built-in sweeper with the specified truncation threshold and saves it in a sparse matrix form. Then it uses Griffin's mesh sweeper to obtain $L^{-1}\vec{R}^l$. Next, the algorithm integrates the resulting vector with the Gauss quadrature to obtain the right hand side in terms of residual source based uncollided scalar fluxes ($WL^{-1}\vec{R}^l$), followed by solving the linear system $\tilde{B}\vec{\Phi} = WL^{-1}\vec{R}^l$ with GMRES. Next, the solution is multiplied by the scattering matrix, and the P operator is applied to adjust the size of the vector, then the mesh sweeper (L^{-1}) is applied on the resulting vector to obtain $L^{-1}P\Sigma_s\tilde{B}^{-1}WL^{-1}\vec{R}^l$. Finally, we sum the result of $L^{-1}\vec{R}^l$ with the vector $L^{-1}P\Sigma_s\tilde{B}^{-1}WL^{-1}\vec{R}^l$ to complete the operation defined in Equation (14).

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1. Accuracy of the LITMM Solver

We tested the accuracy of the LITMM low-order solver as implemented in Griffin using a test problem comprised of two nested cubes. The inner cube (region 2) is 8 cm per side with a total macroscopic cross section $\Sigma_{t2} = 1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The outer region (region 1) is 24 cm to the side with vacuum boundary conditions on all its outer faces, and we varied its macroscopic cross section, Σ_{t1} , between 0.5 – 15 cm^{-1} . We set the scattering ratio $c \equiv \Sigma_s/\Sigma_t = 0.999$ to make the problem challenging, and defined a fixed source of strength 1 $\text{cm}^{-3}.\text{s}^{-1}$ within the inner cube, whereas the outer cube is source-free. In all calculations we used a level-symmetric S_6 quadrature and a mesh of 5,184 tetrahedral elements as shown in Figure 1.

For GMRES, we used a 10^{-10} stopping criterion on the residual relative to the initial guess residual, and we compared the LITMM results with those of high-order DFEM-SN on the same mesh, obtained using Griffin's native solver with relative stopping criterion 10^{-10} . The comparisons between the two solution sets are based on the maximum absolute relative error (MARE) in the low-order solution relative to the

Figure 1. Configuration and tetrahedral mesh of the problem used in the numerical tests.

high-order solution on each mesh. These are plotted in Figure 2 together with LITM's density, defined as the fraction of non-zero matrix entries to the total number of matrix entries.

Figure 2. MARE in LITMM's solution and LITM density as a function of Σ_{t1} and truncation threshold.

The MARE results show that the accuracy of the LITMM solution improves as the truncation threshold decreases. This is expected, as fewer entries would be truncated from the ITM. Also, LITM's density decreases with increasing optical thickness because the coupling between cells weakens. The MARE does not exhibit monotonic behavior as a function of cell optical thickness for two reasons [8]. First, by definition, all off-diagonal entries of $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$ in Equation (8) must be negative. However, the DFEM run used to construct $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$ can generate negative fluxes, reflected as positive off-diagonal entries in ITM and LITM. The balance between the neglected entries' signs is the first source of non-monotonicity. The second reason is the decrease in LITM's density as the optical thickness increases causing truncation of more entries in LITM so that even though the LITM becomes more diagonally dominant the error is higher. Overall, the results show that LITMM is an accurate low-order method with truncation thresholds in the range 10^{-7} - 10^{-9} , whereas 10^{-5} produces inaccurate results.

3.2. LITMM as a Preconditioner

In this section, we evaluate the LITMM as a preconditioner for Richardson iterations in Griffin in terms of computational performance by using the same test problem defined in the previous section. We compared the execution time consumed by Griffin's built-in GMRES preconditioner with nonlinear diffusion accelerations (NDA) and our LITM preconditioned Richardson iterations. We ran the simulations on the same computer equipped with an Intel Xeon Platinum 8480+ CPU, using a single thread at 3.8 GHz. We set the relative and absolute convergence criteria for preconditioned Richardson iterations to 10^{-6} and 10^{-8} , at which point the code stops iterations when either criterion is met. In this context, the LITM preconditioned solution differs from that of Griffin's built-in solvers by at most the iterative stopping criterion, and therefore no accuracy check is needed. While using LITMM as a preconditioner,

we set the convergence criterion for LITMM’s GMRES solver to 10^{-7} . When using Griffin’s built-in GMRES preconditioner, NDA is applied only after a fixed number of GMRES iterations (serves as inner iterations and preconditioner) per Richardson iteration (serves as outer iteration). We determined the optimal fixed number of GMRES iterations per Richardson iteration by testing 1, 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 iterations for each optical thickness value and selected the value that minimized runtime. For optically thick problems, NDA can be unstable unless the inner iteration is sufficiently converged, so the optimal number of GMRES iterations is problem-dependent. The optimal values that were used in our tests are reported in Table I. The comparison of total computational time to converge the Richardson iterations using the LITMM as a preconditioner—including matrix construction, linear-solve cost, and the additional sweeps required by LITMM—to that of Griffin’s built-in GMRES preconditioner with NDA acceleration is shown in Table I. In the comparisons, we define a speed-up parameter, computed as the ratio of the time consumed by Griffin’s built-in solver to that of the LITMM solver.

Table I. Speed-up obtained by the LITM preconditioned Richardson iterations.

$\Sigma_{t1} (cm^{-1})$	Griffin Comp. Time (s)	Opt. Num. GMRES per Richardson	Speed-up by LITM Preconditioned Solver		
			Trun. Threshold = 1E-5	Trun. Threshold = 1E-7	Trun. Threshold = 1E-9
0.5	5.9	1	0.12	0.06	0.04
1.0	5.9	1	0.21	0.09	0.06
2.0	10.8	5	0.44	0.22	0.14
3.0	16.4	10	0.60	0.35	0.18
5.0	27.2	10	1.03	0.70	0.35
7.5	38.1	10	1.87	1.19	0.59
10.0	42.6	20	2.73	1.60	0.81
15.0	54.0	20	3.64	2.41	1.33

Moreover, Table II shows the number of required Richardson iterations with the LITMM as a preconditioner, along with the LITM construction time as a function of Σ_{t1} and truncation threshold.

Table II. LITM construction time and number of Richardson iterations required for convergence.

$\Sigma_{t1} (cm^{-1})$	Truncation Threshold = 1E-5		Truncation Threshold = 1E-7		Truncation Threshold = 1E-9	
	LITM Const. Time (s)	# Rich. Iter.	LITM Const. Time (s)	# Rich. Iter.	LITM Const. Time (s)	# Rich. Iter.
0.5	41.1	5	94.0	3	127.0	2
1.0	20.8	5	51.5	3	88.6	2
2.0	12.5	5	28.4	3	54.2	2
3.0	10.1	6	22.5	3	42.6	3
5.0	7.7	6	16.2	3	30.1	3
7.5	6.2	5	12.2	3	22.2	3
10.0	5.3	5	10.2	3	17.9	3
15.0	4.3	6	8.2	3	13.7	3

The results in Table I show that LITM preconditioned Richardson iterations execute faster than Griffin’s built-in preconditioner with NDA acceleration for optically thick problems ($\Sigma_{t1} \geq 5.0 cm^{-1}$). However, the computational performance of the LITMM as a preconditioner deteriorates as the truncation threshold decreases due to the rapid increase in LITM’s construction time, even though the number of Richardson iterations decreases as shown in Table II. The results in Table II show that the LITM construction time increases considerably as the truncation threshold is tightened because more cells need to be included during the sweeps for the LITM construction. The number of LITM preconditioned Richardson iterations declines as the truncation threshold decreases since the accuracy of the LITM operator improves by lowering the truncation threshold, as shown in Figure 2. To summarize, the results demonstrate that the LITMM preconditioner outperforms Griffin’s built-in preconditioner for optically thick cases when a reasonable truncation threshold is employed.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We developed a low-order integral transport matrix method for the DFEM-SN discretization of the neutron transport equation. We first developed a dynamic truncation algorithm to eliminate negligible entries in the ITM that are below a specified threshold, and defined the LITM operator for DFEM-SN. We implemented the LITMM as a solver in Griffin and assessed its accuracy for a three-dimensional heterogeneous test problem by comparing the low-order solution with a reference high-order solution. The comparisons reveal that using LITMM as a solver can generate solutions with sub-percent error for a wide range of optical thicknesses with truncation thresholds of 10^{-7} and 10^{-9} , and that, for a given threshold, LITM's density decreases monotonically with increasing optical thickness. Further analysis shows that LITMM's solution error increases non-monotonically with optical thickness, due to the sparser matrix structure. Moreover, we implemented LITMM as a preconditioner for the Richardson iterations in Griffin and assessed its computational performance against Griffin's built-in solver. The results show that the LITMM preconditioner executes faster than Griffin's built-in preconditioner for optically thick configurations. The results also suggest that using a reasonable truncation threshold is beneficial when LITMM is employed as a preconditioner for improved computational performance. Overall, we conclude that LITMM can be used as either an accurate low-order method or a computationally efficient preconditioner for Richardson iterations, employing reasonable truncation thresholds. In future work, we plan to extend the LITMM to multi-group eigenvalue problems employing DFEM-SN discretizations in Griffin and to test it with realistic reactor core problem configurations.

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